

preliminary study of rice ratoon patterns in 1976. On a 1,800-m² area, the plant crop or main wet season crop matured in 166 days. It was harvested 30 January and yielded 2.2 t/ha. In the same area, a ratoon crop of the same variety was grown without additional fertilizer and with only natural seepage and residual water. It yielded 1.7 t/ha in 109 days. It was harvested on 18 May, well before the onset of rains, but the regular second crop of Mangala, Baroda, or CH45 was heavily damaged by continuous rains after flowering. The yield of the ratoon crop, which was 77%, of that of the plant crop, was obtained at little additional cost. A few private

farmers in the arcas reported successful ratoon crops of Intan.

Another study of rice ratoon patterns with Intan was conducted on a private farm in Chikmagalur district in the 1977–78 wet season. The experiment was seeded on 10 June 1977, transplanted on 16 July, and harvested on 12 December. The ratoon crop was ready for harvest on 24 April 1978, but was harvested on 2 May because it was maintained as a demonstration crop for visitors.

The ratoon crop – which matured in 133 days – generally yielded more than the plant crop (see table). Ratoon crop yields ranged from 76 to 350% of the plant crop yields. At 0 kg N/ha, they

averaged 93% of the plant crop yield; at 17.5 kg N/ha, 132%, at 25 kg N/ha, 180%; and at 50 kg N/ha, 300%. The ratoon crop had 24% shorter growth duration and 59% higher mean yield than the plant crop.

Because the plant crop treatments were not originally planned for a ratoon crop study, a lack of replications limits the data's value. But the treatment that received the recommended dose of NPK in the wet season and no N in the ratoon crop might be close to an average farm situation. Interestingly ratoon yields were high even in plots where the plant crop yields were low. ■

Productivity and management of farmers' transplanted aman rice on a rainfed double rice cropped area of Bangladesh

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During the 1975 and 1976 aman seasons, crop-cut studies were conducted in farmers' fields in the BRRI project area where 2 rainfed rice crops/year are grown. T. aman is grown after harvest of either direct seeded or transplanted aus rice. The choice of a high yielding variety (HYV) or local variety of T. aman is largely dependent on the preceding crop. Direct seeded local aus crops provide a long growing season for rainfed HYV T. aman. In general, the local photoperiod-insensitive variety is preceded by HYV transplanted aus, while the HYV T. aman is preceded by a short-duration direct-seeded aus rice. Usually a HYV or a local variety of T. aman is transplanted in late July to early August and harvested in November and December.

Rice samples were taken from 5-m² areas in farmers' fields during harvest. Each sample was threshed, cleaned, and weighed, and the moisture content was determined in the field. The yield of each variety was computed at 14% moisture. The farmers were interviewed to determine the level of crop manage-

Data on average productivity and farm management of Transplanted aman rice collected by crop-cuts in the 1975 and 1976 aman seasons, BRRI, Bangladesh.^a

	1975		1976	
	HYV	Local	HYV	Local
Samples (no.)	113	174	28	100
Yield (t/ha)	3.3	2.3	2.8	2.2
Yield range (t/ha)	1.0–4.7	1.2–3.4	1.2–4.3	1.0–3.8
Field duration (days)	116	119	120	113
Plowings (no.)	5.1	5.2	4.9	5.1
Harrowings (no.)	5.4	5.7	5.0	5.6
Date transplanted	3 Aug	31 Aug	31 Jul	16 Aug
Seedling age (days)	37	43	34	44
Farmers using N-P-K (%)	94-84-2	80-75-6	91-57-19	88-76-13
Kate of fertilization (kg N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O/ha)	47-47-15	41-43-31	55-57-37	45-37-34
Farmers that did not weed (%)	20	35	38	53
Farmers that weeded once (%)	46	47	48	41
Farmers that weeded twice (%)	31	16	14	3
Farmers that weeded three (%)	3	2	0	3
Weed control index ^b	1.9	2.4	1.6	2.0
Farmers that used pesticide (%)	36	15	33	18
Monthly rainfall (cm) Aug, Sep, Oct, Nov	25.0, 31.7, 37.4, 0.8		30.5, 17.2, 7.3, 0.8	

^a High yielding varieties were Pajam, IR5, IR20, and BR4. The local varieties were Nizersail, Chandrasail, Chinigura, Larhibilash, Kaocha, Binni, and Tulsimalati. ^b 1 = excellent, and 5 = poor weed control.

ment used in each plot.

The HYV significantly outproduced local varieties in both years (see table); however, variability among samples was larger in 1975 than in 1976. The average productivity of the HYV was about 15% higher in 1975, probably because of the rainfall pattern during flowering and grain filling. The HYVs were transplanted earlier and remained in the field longer than the local varieties. The HYVs are transplanted early to

escape cold during flowering. The local photoperiod-sensitive aman varieties can be transplanted later because they flower before the cold nights begin. Their low yield is attributed mainly to a shorter vegetative phase and fewer tillers per plant.

Farmers generally gave higher management levels and applied more fertilizers at more balanced doses to the HYVs than to the local rices. ■